

Electrochemical Reduction of 8-(2-Cyanoethyl)-8-azabicyclo[3,2,1]oct-3-en-2-one

A. H. EL-ASKALANI, S. A. EL-ABBADY, A. A. AL-AHMADY, A. M. ABOU EL-MAGD and A. H. MOUSTAFA*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Umm Al-Qura University, Makkah Al-Mukarramb, Saudi Arabia

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Polarographic reduction of the conjugated system in 8-(2-cyanoethyl)-8-azabicyclo[3,2,1]oct-3-en-2-one has been investigated in buffer solutions of varying pH's at the dropping mercury electrode. The nature of the electrode reduction and kinetic parameters have been calculated. The pK values were determined by spectrophotometric method. A mechanism for the electrochemical reduction is suggested.

8-Azabicyclo[3,2,1]oct-3-en-2-one have received much attention since it was first synthesised by Kataritzky and Takeuchi¹. Such compounds have potential value as synthons. It has been reported that reduction by normal metal hydrides takes place preferentially at the carbonyl function². However, the catalytic hydrogenation using H₂/Pd-C (10%) at room temperature has been reported by the same authors². The polarographic behaviour of α,β -unsaturated-tropones was the subject of interest³. This led us to investigate the electrochemical reduction of the title compound.

Results and Discussion

Spectrophotometric studies : The uv absorption spectrum of the title compound reveals bands at 225.5 (ϵ 7150 dm³ mol cm, π - π^* transition) and a weak band at 270 nm (800, n - π^* transition). It was shown that the intensity of the former band (i.e. the K-band) increases as the pH increases up to 7.0. At pH's < 7.0 the absorption is more or less constant. Thus, plot of absorbance against pH at 225.5 nm reveals a S-shape with half-height at 4.2 (Fig. 1). This indicates the presence of an acid-base equilibria with a dissociation constant of 4.2. 8-(2-Cyanoethyl)-8-azabicyclo[3,2,1]oct-3-en-2-one has two basic centers, the bridgehead nitrogen atom and the oxygen atom of the carbonyl function ; the former being more basic. Accordingly, at low pH's the protonation could take place at both basic centers to give the dication. As the pH increases the protonation becomes discriminatory to give preferentially the N-protonated species (Scheme 1).

The following acid \rightleftharpoons base equilibrium is suggested,

Fig. 1

Polarographic studies : Polarograms of 2×10^{-4} M azabicyclo[3,2,1]oct-3-en-2-one in Britton-Robinson buffer solutions are illustrated in Fig. 2. At $\text{pH} < 4.15$ the polarogram consists of one wave. The limiting current of this wave, almost constant ($1.06 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{A}$) by increasing the pH from 2.11 to 4.15, corresponds to a 2-electron process ($i = 1 \mu\text{A}$ for 10^{-4} M concentration). At higher pH values ($\text{pH} > 4.15$), the polarogram consists of two waves of equal height at $\text{pH} = \text{p}K_a$, indicating that the two waves are due to separate reduction of conjugate base with the recombination of anion with protons.

Scheme 1

As the pH increases the limiting current of the two waves decreases gradually. This indicates that the reduction process at $\text{pH} < 4.15$ differs from that at higher pHs. Also the number of electrons consumed along each wave are equal at all pH values. The small decrease of the height of the first wave and the appearance of a second wave depends upon the position of the acid base equilibrium of the reducible species as confirmed by spectrophotometric studies.

The slope of $E_{1/2}$ -pH curves amounts 0.077 and 0.054 V for the first and second wave respectively, indicating that one proton is involved in the rate-determining step for electron transfer.

The effect of mercury height on the limiting current of the waves shows that the reduction process is diffusion-controlled in acid media, and diffusion-controlled in addition to adsorption in alkaline media. The α_{na} values and the kinetic parameters K_t and ΔG^* are estimated from the analysis of the waves⁴ at pHs 3.7 and 9. These values (Table 1) indicate the irreversibility of the reduction process and the increase of irreversibility as the pH increases.

Fig. 2

TABLE 1—RESULTS OBTAINED FOR 2×10^{-4} M OF 8-(2-CYANOETHYL)-8-AZABICYCLO IN DIFFERENT pHs

pH	$E_{1/2}$ vs Ag/AgCl/KCl sat.	Slope V^{-1}	α_{na}	k_t $cm\ s^{-1}$	ΔG^\ddagger kcal
3.25	-0.91	12.85	0.76	1.98×10	97.08
6.30	1st wave -1.12	16.68	0.99	9.25×10	163.37
	2nd wave -1.49	14.53	0.86	1.83×10	114.62
10.55	1st wave -1.48	16.35	0.97	2.09×10	166.30
	2nd wave -1.70	11.06	0.65	4.68×10	141.16

The plots of concentration (C in mM) against the diffusion current measured at the plateau position of each wave at pHs 3.1, 5.95 and 9 give straight lines passing through the origin within the concentration range (0.0–0.4 mM). The results confirm the applicability of Ilkovic equation and possible analytical determination of 8-azabicyclo[3,2,1]oct-3-en-2-one within the concentration range under experimental conditions.

Controlled potential electrolysis for 10^{-4} M solution of 8-azabicyclo[3,2,1]oct-3-en-2-one in 0.1 M HCl and in Britton-Robinson buffer of pH 6.0 was monitored by electronic spectra where the absorption band characteristic of the substrate at λ_{max} 225.5 nm completely disappeared. Also the corresponding saturated cycloadduct **2a** was investigated in order to determine the reduction potential of the C=O. It was shown that C=O under the condition of the experiment is not reduced.

From the foregoing results the electroreduction of 8-azabicyclo[3,2,1]oct-3-en-2-one may proceed according to the following mechanism.

(i) At pHs < 4.2 :

(ii) At pHs > 4.2 :

Experimental

*Isomeric 6-endo- and 6-exo-carbonitrile-8-(2-cyanoethyl)-8-azabicyclo[3,2,1]oct-3-en-2-one*²: A mixture of 3-pyridinol (9.5 g, 0.1 mol), acrylonitrile (90 ml) and hydroquinone (0.02 g) was refluxed for 24 h and the excess acrylonitrile was then removed under reduced pressure (5 mm Hg/40°). The cooled residue (oily material) was twice chromatographed on alumina H (neutral) using 3:1 methylene chloride-light petroleum (b.p. 40–60°) and then methylene chloride to give a yellow viscous oil (18 g, 90%). ¹H nmr spectrum of the product revealed that it is a mixture of about 50 : 50 6-*exo* and 6-*endo* stereoisomers, H-5 displayed a doublet at δ 5.07 and a triplet at 5.20 ppm².

The polarograms were recorded on Metrohm Polarecord E 506 and a polarography stand E 505 DC. The capillary characteristics in 0.1 M KCl (open circuit) were $m=0.988/s$ and $t=3.8 s/drop$ at mercury spectrophotometer were used.

All measurements were carried out at room temperature (25°). The stock solution ($10^{-2}M$) was prepared in absolute ethanol. Britton-Robinson⁶ double concentration modified universal buffers were used as supporting electrolytes. The calculated amount of the buffer solution was introduced in the polarographic cell. The solution was deaerated by bubbling dry nitrogen gas for 20 min. The required amount of the stock solution was transferred into the cell and the polarograms recorded while nitrogen gas was passed above the surface.

The uv absorption spectrum of 8-(2-cyanoethyl)-8-azabicyclo[3,2,1]oct-3-en-2-one was measured in ethanol in the range 200–350 nm for $10^{-4}M$ solution in ethanol at different pH values.

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